

Nigerian Military Challenges in the Fight against the Alliance of Isis, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram Terrorist Groups for National Security

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Abstract

Despite the acclaimed success of the Nigerian anti-terror military operations and her collaborators, it is indeed paradoxical that the terror campaign of Boko Haram is yet to abate and is rather becoming more sophisticated, lethal, and producing some other splinter groups. Therefore, this study examines Nigerian military and the challenges in the fight against the alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups for National Security. The study adopted Agency theory. The method of data collection was premised on both primary and secondary methods of data collections. Questionnaire and Personal Interview were employed as instruments for primary data, while for secondary method, sources like research papers, policy papers, documents, journals, magazines, seminars, workshop papers and handbook were utilized. The study finds that corruption has deepened in the armed forces of Nigeria and weakened war against Boko Haram terrorism by stealing of security budgets, the procurement of under- standard arms, the development of bogus military agreement and the lack of logistical support for and desertion of frontline soldiers. This proves that there are many fundamental challenges bedevilling the military in their fight against alliance of the ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups in Nigeria among which is endemic corruption within the Nigerian security system. Therefore, research proposition one is valid and accepted. The study recommends that Nigerian government must recognize that unless issues of bad governance and systemic corruption, especially the problem of political corruption

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stemming from interreligious and interethnic rivalry aimed at the control of the state machinery for economic and political gains, are seriously addressed, all other measures will be nothing but cosmetic and pro tempore.

Keywords: Nigerian, Military, Challenges, Alliance, Terrorist Groups and National Security

INTRODUCTION

National security is an old phenomenon which was first introduced in the United States of America after the Second World War and falls under the traditional school of thought which favours the maintenance of the Cold War conception of security. The report from Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) Transnational Threat Project in 2018 shows that the total group alliances consist of more than sixty Salafi Jihadist groups in 2016 which estimated to have around 200,000 Salafi-Jihadist Fighters. The groups are spread across the globe, such as Europe, East Asia and the Pacific, Middle East, North Africa, Central Asia, South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa. This fact shows that the existence of state actors (states) are under attack. Those terrorist groups insist to establish "Caliphate", a reign of Muslim ruler, to erase modern state system. Today's terrorist groups also possess ability in their operations by utilizing technology. They establish strong network and mobility across the globe. On the other hand, states are still colliding with the application of globalization vis-à-vis sovereignty. State actors mobility are still limited by formal interactions and inflexibility in conducting relations or network. This phenomenon gives advantages to terrorist groups since they can fully operate globalization and create their own borderless world. The power and authority of states in today's globalization and democratization era are declining (Pogoson, 2018).

There have been a series of debate on whether Boko Haram has any external links with foreign organizations such as the ISIS and Al-Qaida. This argument laid to rest in 2003 when the former leader of Al-Qaida (Osama Bin Laden) mentioned Nigeria as one of the countries in Africa to be liberated by the Al-Qaida (MarcAntoine Pérouse de Montclos 2014). Also, a former Ambassador of the US to Nigeria revealed that the armed Jihadists from Mali are part of the insurgents fighting in Nigeria for Boko Haram as mercenaries (Lyman et al., 2004).

The US and UN listing of Boko Haram and Ansaru significantly contributed to the transformation of the widely acknowledged local terrorist groups to international terror groups operating alongside ISIS, Al Qaida, and Al-Shabaab. It is widely believed that Boko Haram fighters just like Al-Shabaab and other related groups fighters were trained in ISIS camps in Mali (WARN, 2013). Furthermore, Connell argues that Boko Haram insurgents were at Al Qaida in Maghreb (AQIM) training camp in Timbuktu

Mali where they learned skills such as servicing Kalashnikovs, shoulder-fired weapons, making and detonation of bombs (Connell, 2012). Furthermore, in 2014, former Nigeria's President Goodluck Jonathan acknowledged that Boko Haram has an international link with other international terror organizations. They run training camps and indoctrination centres in Mali, Niger, Cameroun, Chad, Sudan, and Central African Republic (News Watch, 2014).

Research Objectives

- i. To ascertain the challenges facing Nigerian military in the fight against alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups for National Security.
- ii. To find out the measures adopted by Nigerian government to overcome the challenges facing Nigerian military in the fight against alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups for National Security.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Wara (2020) critically compared the roles of CSOs in fighting terrorism between Nigeria and Tunisia. Functional approach was employed in the analysis. The study placed more emphasis on content analysis to tests the hypothesis that a country with vibrant CSOs is more likely to eradicate terrorism than the one that has not. The study also responded to question that: how effective are the CSOs' anti-terrorism policies in the two countries? The research found out that even though Tunisia has more coordinated CSOs than Nigeria, the roles of the CSOs in both countries is not significant enough to help in getting rid of terrorism. So, there is need of more practical approach such as mediation, espionage or infiltration which this research recommends to the global Civil Societies. However, the measures adopted by Nigerian government to overcome the challenges facing Nigerian military in the fight against the alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups were not addressed.

Panle & Shittu (2021) wrote on the Impact of Multinational Joint Task Force Counter-Operations in the Fight against Boko Haram Insurgency. The collective security theory was adopted for this work because it best explains the activities of the insurgents and the Joint Task Force in the Lake Chad Basin Region. The research adopted the phenomenology research design with the qualitative approach. Data were essentially composed of direct non-participant observation and other secondary sources. The research identified poor funding, logistics and mutual suspicion among member states as some of the impediments

militering against the success of the joint actions against the insurgents. The study therefore suggested that more funds be dedicated to the operations of the MNJTF, while countries of the region do more to address underlining social problems through good governance, they must also askew the age long colonial legacies of mutual suspicion and collaborate more closely in dealing with the mutual threats at hand. However, the study did not make reference to the challenges facing Nigerian military in the fight against the alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups.

[Muhammad, Muhammad & Rifat \(2021\)](#) examined Nigerian Government Responses and Action on Terrorist Activities within the state. The theory of relative deprivation was used. Qualitative research method was adopted. The foundation of the article was a review of counter-terrorism literature, reports, and journals, which was used to help analyzed response of government toward the counter-terrorism operations against the Boko Haram sect. The study concluded that the government's present solution, which is primarily focused on resolving the effects of terrorism, is insufficient and needs a plan resolving the root cause and causes of terrorism in order to overcome the crises. Such a policy includes a government-wide method in which the military extends its activities to limit the sect's operational space. Nigerian government faces multi-dimensional facts of terrorist activities in lower level. Poverty and unemployment are the main reason of terrorism, when people could not full fill their basic needs; they involve such type of activities. So, Government should take serious step to overcome all these roots of evils. There is also need to solve the terrorist activities with political dialogue somewhere. To save the future of young population group in state, Nigeria government should take steps of social mobilization and create awareness on social harmony. Many children in Boko Haram groups have innocent, government must take serious steps for better education of their children. The study was not specific of the measures adopted by Nigerian government to overcome the challenges facing Nigerian military in the fight against the alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted Agency theory. Agency theory also called Stewardship theory was propounded by [Ross \(1973\)](#). The driving concepts in the theory are; control and connectedness. Control is about influence essential for orderly moderation of the actions and behaviours of individuals or groups in the performance of their duty. It connotes discipline and the ability to abide within the boundaries set by the law. To strengthen and ensure better intra and inter organizational coordination and synergy in a network relationship entails adopting appropriate control ([Sriram, Ganesh & Madhumathi, 2013](#)) measures especially where information sharing

and cooperation is needed to foster strong bonds of interdependence between allied organizations.

Network relationship can only be strengthened by creating information ecosystem that allows different agencies working on similar task to coordinate and share information (Stoll, Foot & Edward, 2012). Aside from the above, control engenders harmony and compliance to constituted authority and these are key dynamic property of connectedness which promote sustainable action and success.

Connectedness refers to the internal relationships of actors and components dependencies between stakeholders, units within and outside the organization, local networks of trust, formal and informal associations, social networks, knowledge spill overs, patterns of mobility within and from outside the network. Its absence in interagency or allied agencies has consequences for low motivation, distrust, poor communication, institutional flaws (ICG, 2014) conflicting personal or group interest that in the end hampers the achievement desired of goals. Opportunistic behaviour that arises from as a result of its absence is better captured by the agency theory. The theory sees the relationship between the principal and the agent as contractual one which involves delegation of some decision making authority to the agent by the principal. The relationship between the state and the agent is one of the oldest and commonest codified modes of social interactions (Ross, 1973).

To appropriately uphold order and deliver social stability, funding must align with, and strengthen organizational capacity of those state agencies to perform their responsibility rightly. In essence, the state must not only provide, protect and ensure that such funds are judiciously used, but must enforce its accountability so as facilitate connectedness within and among the agencies involved in restoring social order. Real connectedness induces the concord of interest and functionality. It also demands that funding should align with assigned responsibility, ensuring its proper use and accountability; this is necessary, and in part, forms the basic dimension of an agency relationship. This is indispensable considering that different actors are involved and that they have different interests that are likely to be expressed in conflicting preferences (Scott & Marshall, 2005), if it is not properly controlled it is detrimental to the attainment of the goal being pursued. The failure to build-on and entrench the ideals of connectedness has allowed these differences to deepened as each agency wants to illegally have a share of the funds appropriated for curbing insurgency; despite the

consequence that such opportunistic behaviours may have on the society. This is the main problem that has undermined Nigeria's capacity to effectively stamp out insurgency thereby necessitating the government to seek for external assistance. It is disheartening to note that since 2009 to date the federal budgeted allocation for combating insurgency has been on the increase yet, the successes recorded is low compared to the about \$6 billion of public funds spent for the purpose in just four years with an unimpressive outcome to show for it.

There is no single security agency that can maintain peace and security in isolation, but through collaborated efforts and synergy with other security agencies, peace and security can be attained. In other words, the security agencies are the critical components of every government; they are saddled with the herculean task of maintaining law and order, as well as protecting lives and properties of the citizenry. Meanwhile, states function through various selected agencies assigned with respective tasks for the good life of the citizenry. Thus, different agencies perform different tasks such as education, poverty alleviation, environmental sanitation, water supply, health, housing etc. Some of these agencies have overlapping roles and duplicated duties. As a result, they are often engulfed in jurisdiction conflict and animosity. However, inter-agency squabble is more prominent amongst the security agencies (Odoma, 2014). These are agencies saddled with the maintenance of peace and security, as well as the protection of life and property in every political community.

The relevance of the theory to the study is that it explained the impact of corruption on interagency effort to eradicate insurgency and administratively, this can be seen in the lack of effective agency control and connectedness. The frail interagency connectedness has continued to affect the focus of the various security agencies as reflected in-fighting between top military officers, collusion and sabotage with the Boko-Haram by some officer who inform the sect about military intended operational plans against Boko-Haram cells, and diversion of funds meant for the successful execution of the anti insurgency campaign to personal use by top military officers.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the mixed method other wisely known as qualitative and quantitative research design. The target population of this study comprises of Command and Control Center of the Joint Task Force (JTF), Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF), Institute for Peace & Conflict Resolution, Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA), members of community and stakeholders (traditional rulers) in Borno, Yobe and Adamawa state making 4,484 staff of the above mentioned institutions. The sample size was determined using Rakesh statistical formula to arrive at 400.

The methods of data collection in this research are both primary and secondary. In-depth interview and 5 point Likert Scale questionnaire was utilize for this investigation making provision for respondents to tick either strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagree, disagreed and indifferent /undecided. The study also considered the close ended questionnaire. Purposive sampling technique was employed for the selection of interview respondents while simple random technique was used for the distribution of questionnaire. Data from questionnaire was analysed quantitatively using simple percentages and frequency distribution while the deductive thematic analysis approach was used for analysing the data sourced from interview.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Four hundred (400) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents who are officers of Command and Control Center of the Joint Task Force (JTF), Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF), Institute for Peace & Conflict Resolution, Office of the National Security Adviser(ONSA), members of community and stakeholders (traditional rulers) in Borno, Yobe and Adamawa state out of which three hundred and eighty - nine (389) copies of questionnaire were completely filled and retrieved while eleven (11) copies of the questionnaire were not returned. However, the analysis is presented based on the premise of retrieved 389 and found fit for analysis.

The responses from questionnaire were presented according to the objectives using frequency table (frequency, count and percentage). Interviews were held with six (6) staff from the above mentioned organizations. The interview results were supplemented with information from the extant literature, including newspapers, reports, and official documents.

Table 1: Challenges facing Nigerian Military in the Fight against the Alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram Terrorist Groups

Constraints	Frequency	%
Poor security framework	102	26
Proliferation of arms and weapon of mass destruction	91	23
Corruption	83	21
Weak international support	99	25
All of the Above	14	5
Total	389	100

Source: Field Work, February (2023)

The table above present data on challenges facing Nigerian Military in the Fight against the Alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram Terrorist Groups; it shows that one hundred and two (102) respondents representing twenty-six (26) percent indicated poor security framework, ninety-nine (99) respondents accounting for twenty-five (25) percent pointed at weak international support, ninety-one (91) respondents accounting twenty-three (23) percent ticked proliferation of arms and weapon of mass destruction, while eighty-three (83) respondents representing twenty-one (21) percent indicated corruption. Those who agreed to all the above mentioned options are fourteen (14) or five (5) percent. This is further supported by the following interview responses and related secondary information on the challenges facing Nigerian Military in the Fight against the Alliance of ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram Terrorist Groups.

Tactically and operationally, there is very little the MNJTF can do, since it is only as strong as its members. It lacks both intelligence architecture and operational standby force it could willingly deploy in counter-terrorism operations. Hence the bureaucratic bottle neck involved in mobilizing fighting force whenever the need arises slowed down the progress of the Joint Task Force and its efficiency in the face of Boko Haram attacks. Nigeria's neighbours like Cameroon and Chad who are also affected by the terrorist activities do belong to LCBC but do not belong to ECOWAS the regional organization, which means that there is the need for trans-national response rather than only LCBC (February 9th, 2023).

Migration remains one of the challenges confronting Nigeria to deal with the issue of Boko Haram decisively, and this primarily due to its size, corruption, and bad leadership. Nigeria is ranked 3rd after Syria and Ivory Coast in terms of illegal migration to Europe and other parts of the world. The long history of migration issue with the Nigerian nationals, the International Organization for Migration Nigeria, is presently implementing the policy framework program funded by the European Commission titled 'Promoting Better Management of Migration in Nigeria. The IOM draw three mechanisms to fully implement the program; Migration Data, Policy, and Labour Migration and Diaspora Mobilization. As part of the effort to curtail migration, the IOM established migration monitoring units in the critical northern states of Kano and Sokoto to gather intelligence about the influx of people into the region. A particular state of concern, 'Borno' that supposed to have a migration monitoring point because it bordered three states of Cameroon, Chad, and Niger, which serves as the migratory route, has no such unit. Although, it was asserted that some points would be established soon to further countered illegal migration. This is regarded as a critical development in fighting border crimes (February 6th, 2023).

In the area of border security, relevant agencies such as immigration, custom, police, and the military cooperate and share intelligence. The threats of Boko Haram and other social vices prompted the Nigerian authority to impose some stringent measures at its border. Data collection and analysis requires a systematic, integrated review to avoid errors and preconception. Lack of modern equipment for the person charged with the responsibility to monitor migration staunchly affects their operational capability. Also, apart from the agencies' equipment, the government owns its part failed to exercise any form of control of its border, which indicates a severe and challenging situation to reduce the threat of cross-border crimes, such as terrorism, kidnapping, and other security challenges.

Obasi (2015) rightly observed that there was a time when “soldiers and units refuse to fight because they are ill-equipped; and some commanders complain that they lack logistics, including helicopters they need to deploy and reinforce their troops in remote locations and evacuate them speedily, if necessary. Part of this problem of equipment is due to corruption in procurement processes and poor maintenance of assets on ground. The cumulative effect of all these is that morale is low. The soldiers are less motivated to fight than the insurgents.” Of course, the root of this less motivation is not even military welfare or even taken care of their family, but ‘under-equipped’ as an analyst observed “the major problem the soldiers have is they don’t have the equipment to fight,” (Robertson, 2015).

Table 2: Responses on the measures adopted by Nigerian government to overcome the challenges facing Nigerian military in the fight against the alliance of ISIS, Alqa’eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups

Measures	Frequency	%
Terrorism Prevention Act 2011 and 2013	79	20
Multi National Joint Task Force (MNJTF)	71	18
Declaration of the state of emergency	55	14
Civilian JTFs have been established	69	18
Invest heavily in security equipment	51	13
All of the Above	64	17
Total	389	100

Source: Field Work, February (2023).

The table above present responses on the measures adopted by Nigerian government to overcome the challenges facing Nigerian military in the fight against the alliance of

ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups; data shows that seventy-nine (79) respondents representing twenty (20) percent indicated Terrorism Prevention Act 2011 and 2013, seventy-one (71) respondents accounting for eighteen (18) percent pointed at Multi National Joint Task Force (MNJTF), sixty-nine (69) respondents accounting eighteen (18) percent indicated that civilian JTFs have been established, while sixty-four (64) respondents representing seventeen (17) percent indicated all of the above mentioned options. Fifty-one (51) respondents representing fourteen (14) percent indicated the declaration of the state of emergency. Those who indicated invest heavily in security equipment are fifty-one (51) or thirteen (13) percent.

Like all the counterterrorism measures, the goal is to halt or suppress all acts of terror in the land; addressing the structural, geographical, and operational susceptibilities of the terrorists remains critical to all governments. In this regard, we have seen how the Nigerian government, civil society organizations, and international organizations partner with Nigeria to adopt a global best practice in confronting Boko Haram menace and other insecurity 'soft approach'. This widely employed approach by many states facing security problems is perceived as a development strategy, not a traditional military approach. The coercive military approach in dealing with extremism is not only central to the Nigerian government but synonymous in almost all states ([February 10th, 2023](#)).

He elaborated further that there is a notion that a military approach in suppressing Boko Haram acts is responsible for the group becoming violent in their struggle. He opined that the limitations and disadvantages of engaging the military in the fight against terrorism are however numerous: the impact of military incursion on innocent civilians is so disconcerting primarily when they aimed to strike terrorists' operations. Apart from the victims of the violence, loss of infrastructure and hardship people experience will prefer to remain under the siege of the terrorists. For instance, at the height of Boko Haram insurgency, victims encountered serious adversity that resulted in venting their resentment on the military and began to sympathize and support the terrorists. In my interaction with some victims of the carnage in Yola, Adamawa State, they opined that the level of hardship and suffering they are going through is better for the carnage to continue since it cannot prevent them from seeking the means of livelihood.

Another participant noted that ground forces have been a major aspect of the military response, particularly in south-central Borno, where Operation Deep Punch I and II have seen a number of incursions into the Sambisa Forest area. In addition, the use of air power through a series of operations called Ruwan Wuta (Rain of Fire) has also been an important aspect. With little information coming out of the northern parts of Borno state, including Marte and

Abadam LGAs which remain off-limits, it is difficult to assess the campaign against ISIS-WA. In one sense, this has been because of the nature of JAS itself. JAS has been responsible for more frequent but less deadly suicide assaults, especially those conducted by underage or female bombers, which tend to attract significant media attention and occur on a near-daily basis in the region. The frequent targeting of civilians also demands a more robust response than ISIS-WA's less frequent attacks on security forces (February 7th, 2023).

Another respondent responded that International law has responded to the fight against terrorism through the United Nations Charter and a series of international law instruments. International human rights instruments have also been brought to the fore in the fight against the insurgency's continuous rise. The Nigerian government has employed policy strategies and legal frameworks and numerous countermeasures directed at addressing the insurgency of Boko Haram. Human rights appeared to be implicated in the process, either in the form of failure to protect citizens from Boko Haram operations or violations of human rights in the course of the implementation of measures to check insurgencies (February 9th, 2023).

In response to the opprobrious acts of Boko Haram, an act of the parliament was enacted by the two chambers of Nigeria's National Assembly in 2011 and later amended in 2013. The act is known as the Terrorism Prevention Act. The act made explicit provisions of various crimes of terrorism and other related crimes and what can be dealt with according to the stipulated laws. The Act addressed prevention, prohibition, and combating terrorism and, principally, funding of terrorism and terrorism-related crimes. It also provides for the rigorous implementation of the Convention on the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism and Convention on the Suppression of the Financing of Terrorism and defined penalties to anyone that violates the provisions of the act. The Act, however, has vague provisions affecting its effective implementation. Human rights violations arising from terrorism and counterterrorism have been a significant concern in Nigeria, thereby questioning the approach adopted in the existing legal framework on counterterrorism in Nigeria. Thus the activities of Boko Haram continue to challenge the realization of human rights as well as the effort of the government to address the menace.

Traditionally, the Nigerian government is known in constituting committees to do fact finding in any matter of significant magnitudes such as conflicts and other upheavals. When the government realized that military approach alone

cannot solve or suppress Boko Haram conflict it resorted to a soft method by constituting a presidential committee to unravel the root causes of their struggle, as well as adopt another means to address the conflict. Previously, the government perceived the conflict as a political struggle between aggrieved politicians in the aftermath of the 2011 general elections, but the situation proves otherwise. The presidential committee was regarded as one of the unconventional approaches for countering Boko Haram conflict. The ingredients contained in the committee's findings and recommendations lies mostly on political and development strategy. Substantial parts of the proposal are captured in the NACTEST document. The committee emphasizes much on the economic empowerment of the restive youths who were viciously used by politicians in the electioneering time as thugs. This factor was considered as the cornerstone that led to the emergence of Boko Haram taking arms against the state. The committee, among other things recommended the thorough investigation into the arbitrary abuse of human rights perpetrated by the security operatives, especially the extra-judicial killing of the founder of the group Mohammed Yusuf, engaging in dialogue with the critical interested party and compensate the victims of the carnage (February 7th, 2023).

Furthermore, [Burt \(2016\)](#) revealed that various civil organizations have partnered with the government to ensure that the authority enacts a law to regulate the activities and operation of Islamic religion, particularly in northern Nigeria. For instance, the Centre for Peace Initiative Development (CEPID) has commenced such a move by engaging some Muslim organizations to work out modalities in that regard. The plan aimed at regulating the way some scholars preach and propagate and interpret their understanding of the Quranic message. We could also see how the civil organization societies are supporting government counterterrorism policies and strategies through media sensitization, peace building, and conflict resolution via dialogue, economic empowerment, and skill acquisition programme, as well as promoting inter-agency and civil-military dialogue, among others. The soft approach is people-oriented and humanly capable than the use of brute force by the military-it is again better than the piece of human rights legislation laid by the international, regional, and domestic instruments.

Through collaborations and alliances, they are able to intervene in resolving critical problems affecting a given community especially where government's hand could not have reached. One of the areas where Civil Society takes a bold step in modern society is fighting terrorism. They help in eradicating the menace of terrorism through awareness, damnation, motivation, appraise, rehabilitation, partnership, indoctrination and co-ordinational approaches ([Buba, 2019](#)).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

1. The study finds that corruption has deepened in the armed forces of Nigeria and weakened war against Boko Haram terrorism by stealing of security budgets, the procurement of under- standard arms, the development of bogus military agreement and the lack of logistical support for and desertion of frontline soldiers. This proves that there are many fundamental challenges bedevilling the military in their fight against alliance of the ISIS, Alqa'eda and Boko Haram terrorist groups in Nigeria among which is endemic corruption within the Nigerian security system. Therefore, research proposition one is valid and accepted. The finding also corroborates with the [Aljazeera \(2020\)](#) which states that Shekau boasted that the Nigerian government could not withstand them because of their alliance with ISIS and Al-Qaeda, who provides them with all the myths needed to confront the government.

[Duke, Agbaji & Bassey, \(2017\)](#) analyses the level of corruption in armed forces of Nigeria, this level of corruption able to disrupt a war against terrorism by Boko Haram in Nigeria. It shows that misery, corruption and injustice are responsible for the growth of Boko haram in Nigeria. Also, [Obasi \(2015\)](#) rightly observed that there was a time when "soldiers and units refuse to fight because they are ill-equipped; and some commanders complain that they lack logistics, including helicopters they need to deploy and reinforce their troops in remote locations and evacuate them speedily, if necessary. Part of this problem of equipment is due to corruption in procurement processes and poor maintenance of assets on ground. The cumulative effect of all these is that morale is low. The soldiers are less motivated to fight than the insurgents."

2. Ground forces have been a major aspect of the military response, particularly in south-central Borno, where Operation Deep Punch I and II have seen a number of incursions into the Sambisa Forest area. In addition, the use of air power through a series of operations called Ruwan Wuta (Rain of Fire) has also been an important aspect. Troops have been reinforced - The international joint task force has taken over the provision of internal security (declaration of the state of emergency) - A curfew has been imposed - GSM services have been banned and restored - Civilian JTFs have been established - Roadblocks have been set up - Invest heavily in security equipment, bomb detector units, communications and transport; and the Chinese CCTV system. The Nigerian government has

employed policy strategies and legal frameworks such as the Terrorism Prevention Act 2011 and 2013 and numerous countermeasures directed at addressing the insurgency of Boko Haram.

CONCLUSION

The Boko Haram group's numerical strength and capacity to challenge the mighty Nigerian army, who are regionally known to be strong and powerful, suggested that they have allies who provide them with sophisticated weapons and logistics. Particularly, it was found that Boko Haram receives both financial and material contributions from external sources, especially from their fellow terrorist organizations such as Al-Qaeda and its affiliate Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM).

Boko Haram has raised global awareness because of its link with Al-Qaeda and ISIS, with the international community considering measures that should be employed to fight the menace of these terrorist groups. Nigeria and the neighbouring States of Chad, Niger and Cameroon have experienced series of attacks. Boko Haram has been labelled a terrorist group, with the US State Department designating it a Foreign Terrorist Organization (FTO) in 2013. The Nigerian government has employed various countermeasures to address the exacerbation of the Boko Haram insurgency using the police, military, and joint operations with the affected countries in Africa such as Chad and Cameroon respectively. Human rights appeared to have been implicated in the current state of affairs. The state's socio-economic development platform cannot reign without security. The threat posed by Boko Haram has led to the breakdown of law and order which seriously affected both government and private sector businesses. The responsibility of providing security of life and property lies with the government and hence, when such security is guaranteed, then have stable political and economic development.

Boko Haram's operations in alliance with ISIS, Alqa'eda have been on-going with much sophistication, leading to loss of lives, property, and peaceful coexistence in Nigeria and its neighbouring states, particularly in Chad and Cameroon. International law has responded to the fight against terrorism through the United Nations Charter and a series of international law instruments. International human rights instruments have also been brought to the fore in the fight against the insurgency's continuous rise. The Nigerian government has employed policy strategies and legal frameworks such as the Terrorism Prevention Act 2011 and 2013 and numerous countermeasures directed at addressing the insurgency of Boko Haram.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The Nigerian government must recognize that unless issues of bad governance and systemic corruption, especially the problem

of political corruption stemming from interreligious and interethnic rivalry aimed at the control of the state machinery for economic and political gains, are seriously addressed, all other measures will be nothing but cosmetic and pro tempore.

- ii. The fact is that if Nigeria wants to defeat Boko Haram and other terrorist groups such as the herdsmen and others, a comprehensive overhaul of the counterterrorism strategy should be carried out to include a civil-military coalition, sharing of vital security information to some critical civilian elements within the community. Although, the army created a department related to that, and a unit exists at the Office of the National Security Adviser to the President. However, the reality is that such units exist only by name as the security operative in the field doesn't relate with the civilians to have the first-hand information from the community relating to security threats. Also, member states of the Lake Chad Region must do more to address the underlining social problem of injustice, poverty, illiteracy, unemployment and bad governance among them that make it easy for the recruitment of youths into terrorism.

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